

Published as: Luckman, Susan 2018, 'Craft Entrepreneurialism and Sustainable Scale: The persistence and evolution of creative challenges to capitalist growth', *Cultural Trends*, 27(5): 313-326.

DOI 10.1080/09548963.2018.1534574

Craft Entrepreneurialism and Sustainable Scale: Resistance to and disavowal of the creative industries as champions of capitalist growth

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Abstract: Craft and design-led creative practices are presently enjoying a zeitgeist moment of popularity, driven by consumer demand for unique, innovative and/or handmade objects. However despite the capacity to scale-up, craftspeople and designer makers continue to challenge conventional capitalist ideas of what entrepreneurial 'success' looks like. Drawing upon data from a 4 year study of Australian designer makers, this article problematizes the digital content-friendly growth and enterprise discourses at the heart of governmental desires for the creative economy; discourses that seemingly presume every entrant into the creative field aspires to be the multi-millionaire director of their own creative success story. It examines how the complex intersectionality of old understandings of artistic value and 'doing what you love', today mingle with ethical consumption values, environmental attentiveness, non-urban creative practice, the gendered exclusions of the creative workforce, and human desires for 'good work' (Hesmondhalgh and Baker 2011), to present a more complex, socially-embedded picture of the contemporary creative economy. One where the more-than-capitalism values of the arts and cultural industries persist.

Introduction

Craft and design-led creative practices are presently enjoying a zeitgeist moment of popularity, driven by consumer demand for unique, innovative and/or handmade objects. Traditional understandings of entrepreneurial success would assume that the aim of the majority of these makers as they pursue their creative careers is to ultimately be in a position to scale-up their production while stepping back from the making themselves; a take on the hegemonic story of digital start-up success growing from a garage, or of being able to sell one's once small-batch gin company to one of the liquor distribution majors. However despite the capacity to scale-up, especially at the more design rather than craft end of the spectrum of practice, craftspeople and designer makers continue to challenge conventional capitalist ideas of what entrepreneurial 'success' looks like. Drawing upon data from a 4 year study of Australian designer makers, this article problematizes the digital content-friendly growth and enterprise discourses at the heart of governmental desires for the creative economy; discourses that seemingly presume every entrant into the creative field aspires to be the multi-millionaire director of their own creative success story. It examines how the complex intersectionality of old understandings of artistic value and 'doing what you love', today mingle with ethical consumption values, environmental attentiveness, non-

urban creative practice, the gendered exclusions of the creative workforce, and human desires for 'good work' (Hesmondhalgh and Baker 2011), to present a more complex, socially-embedded picture of the contemporary creative economy. One where the more-than-capitalism values of the arts and cultural industries persist.

Creative Entrepreneurialism: Neoliberal Dreams for Cultural and Creative Work

The increasing absence of secure employment options in the neoliberal workplace demands greater individual responsibility for generating work of workers themselves, leading for many to the setting up of a micro-enterprise and/or engaging in self-employment in the absence of other employment options (Adkins 2012; Banks and Milestone 2011; Beck and Beck-Gernsheim 2002; Duffy 2017; McRobbie 2007). In the bespoke contemporary creative economy and in an age of 'context collapse' (Marwick and Boyd 2011), online marketing, supply and distribution channels manageable from the kitchen table have normalised entrepreneurial business practices in middle class homes across the industrialised world. One of the many ways in which the "ordinary and normalised presence of financial capitalism", including its "entrepreneurial subjectivities" has seeped into the everyday of the domestic and home-life (Allon 2014, p. 13), leading to growing markets for support services such as start-up bank loans and do-it-yourself online shopfronts. In Australia the rise of entrepreneurial discourses around cultural work has occurred in parallel with significant cuts to government funding at both the state and federal level for arts and culture. This rather dire situation is further reflected in the current absence of any national craft and/or design support organisation, nor national cultural policy. This void has in part been filled with business-development support, including notably in our study the New Enterprise Incentive Scheme (NEIS) - a form of welfare support available to the otherwise unemployed to provide small business development assistance to those deemed to have a commercially viable idea. In a brochure released to celebrate 30 years of the scheme, the 'can do' entrepreneurial culture (Naudin and Patel 2017), as well as growth and enterprise assumptions underpinning this small business support are made explicit in the opening message from the Minister for Employment: "Australians are well known for their 'have a go' attitude. The NEIS is a great way to ensure those who are out of work can transition into a situation whereby they are not only gainfully employ themselves but are also creating jobs for fellow Australians." (Senator the Hon Michaela Cash, quoted in Australian Government 2016, p. 5).

On the face of it, all this is the logical extension of the neoliberal dreams underpinning the emergence of creative industries as a creative economy discourse that brought together the more easily scalable digital content creation industries, with what had more often been referred to as the cultural industries and/or arts sector. This move has been written about at great length and I do not have space to revisit these debates here (O'Connor 2010; Pratt, 2005), but suffice to say that the shift to creative *industries* was part of a governmental strategy of justifying funding cuts to large sectors of the arts and cultural sector, and instead emphasising the need for the sector to become more entrepreneurial and self-funding. Where funding was seen as required "this would be spoken of as an investment with an anticipated return, rather than a subsidy offered to some supplicant, grant-dependent entity" (Ross 2007, p. 24). Consequently, alongside the digital content start-ups, the gladiatorial, masculine figure of the business entrepreneur entered the creative terrain. All individuals were, as we know, increasingly expected to become 'entrepreneurs of the self' given "[g]overnment action, in the creative industries model, is aimed at stimulating and liberating the

latent, or untutored, entrepreneurial energies that lie in reserve in every pocket of cultural activity; a hand up, in other words, rather than a handout.” (Ross 2007, p. 26)

Over twenty years later, we now see the perceived need for entrepreneurial skills education for creative higher education graduates in even those sectors of the cultural and creative industries perhaps previously considered most impervious to them, such as arts and crafts (see Raffo, C., Banks, M., Lovatt, A. and O’Connor, J. 2000 for a critical discussion of this). As McRobbie has written, the ‘creative business school’

is a transformative project [that] seeks to maximize the value of creativity by means of human capital and self-entrepreneurship. The subjects of this new society model are expected to be endlessly flexible and fleet of foot when it comes to opportunities and possibilities in what is now not so much a business environment as a cultural world. This is a way of producing a new workforce for the precarious creative economy. (2016, p. 187)

In this context while the call for entrepreneurial training as part of tertiary arts and other creative degrees can be defended as simply educating creative graduates ‘in the game’ so that they can try and negotiate it as they desire, it sets up false expectations around meritocratic level playing fields and equal access (Littler 2017). Such an approach is also at best a contemporary take on the de Certeauian tactic (de Certeau, 1988), a stance to claw back something in the face of more powerful strategies of economic organisation, contemporary labour management and declining arts and cultural sector funding. It is precisely within such a context that increasing numbers of the middle classes are seeking out creative micro-enterprise as the least worst option, many of them women.

Gender and Creative Entrepreneurialism

While decades of feminist critique have variously challenged the hetero-normative masculine ideals implicit in the ‘risk-taking’, gladiatorial—‘Trump-esque’—entrepreneurial figure (see for example Dy et al. 2017; Essers, et al. 2017; Lewis 2013; Marlow and Dy 2018; Naudin 2018; Naudin and Patel 2017; Rouse et al. 2013; Swail and Marlow 2018), a number of commentators are increasingly arguing that contemporary female and post-Fordist – or ‘hyper-capitalist’ (Yeatman 2014) – entrepreneurial subjectivities are actually far less hostile to one another than we may otherwise imagine (Hassoun 2012; Yeatman 2014). Indeed Gill identifies post-feminism as ‘a distinctive sensibility linked to neoliberalism’ (2011, p. 64). Similarly, others have argued that (educated) women are the contemporary (precarious, flexible) workforce’s ‘ideal entrepreneurial’ subjects (Eisenstein 2009; Gill and Scharff, 2011) or ‘privileged subjects of social change’ (McRobbie 2009, p. 15), as well as noting the emergence of feminized models of entrepreneurialism (Duffy 2017; Duffy and Pruchniewska 2017). Importantly here is how discourses of ‘control’ and ‘choice’, often enabled by new technologies, strongly speak to women’s desires including the reconciliation of paid work and family responsibilities (Yeatman 2014, p. 85).

Significantly in terms of this paper, this hoped for control of work-life relationships is embodied in the rising figure of the ‘mumpreneur’, who embraces rather than contests the role of ‘mother’ as “a business practice that attempts to recast the boundaries between productive and reproductive work” (Ekinsmyth 2011, p. 104; see also Duberley and Carrigan 2012; Ekinsmyth 2011, 2012, 2013,

2014; Nel, Maritz and Thongprovati 2010). More than simply a category that encompasses any woman who happens to be simultaneously a mother and small business entrepreneur, mumpreneurs explicitly seek creative ways to merge the 'spatialities of mothering with those of business practice' in order to accommodate and prioritise the former (Ekinsmyth 2011, p. 105). In short, they are a 'group of entrepreneurs whose self-defined rationales and drivers originate predominantly or significantly from the realm of "reproduction" rather than "production"' (Ekinsmyth 2011, p. 104).

Crafting Middle Class Employment in a Precarious Labour Market

It is within this larger socio-economic context that perhaps unsurprisingly "[c]rafts are currently being rediscovered not only as a hobby but also as a desirable enterprise" (Jakob 2013, p. 127). The empirical data informing the rest of this paper is drawn from a four-year study of Australian designer-makers and craftspeople investigating how online distribution is changing the environment for operating a creative micro-enterprise, and with it, the larger relationship between the public and private spheres. In this project, we recognise that not all handmade micro-entrepreneurs are at the same stage of their career or have the same origin story. Therefore, this qualitative, mixed methods national research project consists of three parallel data collection activities: semi-structured interviews with established makers; a three-year annual interview monitoring of arts, design and craft graduates as they seek to establish their making careers; and a historical overview of the support mechanisms available to Australian handmade producers. This article draws upon findings from both the Emerging and Established Maker categories, for while the latter may have more financial resources to draw upon, experience of negotiating the trade-offs required, or a previous life and career they are able to define their current self-employment in relation to, Emerging Makers at the start of their career also clearly often define quality of life and ethical commitments as central to their business aspirations. At the time of writing, the project had interviewed 20 peak and/or industry organisations, 81 Established Makers, and had almost completed the third and final round of interviews with Emerging Makers (Year 1/'1-Up' = 32; Year 2/'2-Up' = 27; Year 3/'3-Up' = 19). The project employs this phenomenological approach to offer a rich and yet also broad 'insider' perspective on creative micro-enterprise. Interviews remain a valuable tool to account for the grounded, individual experience of creative labour (Hesmondhalgh and Baker 2011; Luckman, Gibson and Lea 2009), allowing for the voices of the researched community to emerge in the study. This has enabled us to capture how creative micro-enterprise is positioned as a work/life model identified as personally and environmentally sustainable, and located within the growing alternative economic networks afforded by the growth of the internet (Gibson-Graham 2006). This is important for despite the emergence of the creative industries as a policy and economic framework for developing the creative sector, within sections of the more traditional arts and craft community a strong reluctance to embrace a business or entrepreneurial approach to sustaining one's practice remains. Therefore semi-structured interviews of this kind are the best tool available for capturing the work/life stories of creative practitioners in their own words. The interviews are all professionally transcribed then thematically coded in NVivo as part of an inductive analysis process.

What clearly emerges in this project's findings is that contemporary makers are in the spirit of contemporary neoliberalism pursuing DIY ('Do It Yourself') or 'self-starter' (Duffy and Pruchniewska 2017, p. 843) entrepreneurial career paths. Not waiting for opportunities to fall into their lap, they

have internalised the belief that they need to make them for themselves, as is increasingly required and expected of the enterprising neoliberal subject. For better or worse, even the self-identified shy or introverted among them, who would just rather get on with their creative practice in splendid isolation, recognise the need for and learn the performative and discursive skills necessary to present their story and themselves as key to the value of the artisanal or handmade items that they sell. The affordances of social media and the baseline of needing to have a personal website are key drivers here. Graduates, through their higher education training, and established makers, through either word of mouth networks, their own writing/promotional skills, or targeted training sessions offered by professional and practice-centred associations, all variously are made to engage with the entrepreneurial self-branding required to operate in this highly aestheticized, self-performative, thoroughly Instagrammable marketplace. But while such self-branding is recognised as being ‘the norm’ or simply what’s required as an entry level baseline, not all makers embrace the practice. Rather they employ a number of tactics in order to de-personalise their business, moving identification of it away from them and perhaps onto, for example, a disembodied brand name. Or they may simply resist and pay the professional and economic cost.

Negotiations such as desiring to remove the self from promotion and letting the products ‘speak for themselves’, reflect the tensions many makers have with the kinds of self-promotional techniques increasingly presumed in the entrepreneurial creative economy. This wider uneasy relationship with the capitalist market process notably leads to a rejection of any identification with entrepreneurialism as a desirable quality, let alone as a descriptor of themselves or what they do, among the majority of designer makers we spoke with. Drawing upon the 179 interviews completed thus far, it is possible to identify at least five distinct ways in which contemporary craftspeople and designer makers resist—generally from positions of class and racial privilege—the entrepreneurial imperatives otherwise presumed of idealised neoliberal subjects:

- I. Refutation of identification with the idea of ‘entrepreneurship’;
- II. Focussing on handmaking and imposing limits to business growth;
- III. Stage of life-related reasons for starting a creative business: ‘downshifting’ not ‘starting up’;
- IV. Quality handmaking as an environmentally-sympathetic response to a world of ‘too much stuff’ and climate crisis;
- V. Still artists at heart: doing ‘what you love’ (which isn't running a business).

I. Refutation of identification with the idea of ‘entrepreneurship’

Across the 179 interviews we have conducted so far, the term ‘entrepreneur’/‘entrepreneurial’ rarely arises. When it does, it is often offered as a prompt for discussion by the interviewer, but then summarily rejected by the research participants, who, on the whole, emphasise they are not ‘looking to take over the world’. For example:

“I think you just need to be really driven and motivated and sensible. I think you need to just realize that you’re not going to get rich overnight. I probably am never going to

be rich but that's okay because that's not what I want to be. I just want to make a full time living from my business." (Female, Established Maker, Textiles)

"A: it might end up as a salad server or a bowl or whatever, but it's always motivated by the context that it's moving towards and something in me that I want to explore. So yeah, so I mean I don't ever make a division between craft art and designing in the interiority of my practise, it's only once it becomes a social object that I start to negotiate those terms in an opportunistic way. Internally I define myself as an artist who works through a medium of craft and design to achieve work. Those things become politically loaded when you put it out there, but I am opportunistic in that sense because I'm not ideologically motivated in my work.

Q: Entrepreneurial?

A: Maybe, I think I'm a very poor entrepreneur to be honest with you." (Male, Established Maker, Metal Design)

Q. So, you're deliberately keeping it at a particular scale?

A: That's right; I want to do the creative stuff. I don't want to be stuck being a manager. I'm not an entrepreneur. It's not what I am." (Female, Established Maker, Textiles)

II. Focussing on handmaking and imposing limits to business growth

Within the field of craft, a key site of boundary contestation comes into play around the respondents' perceived status as makers or craftspeople, and certainly the legitimacy as purveyors of the handmade, of those who choose (or are perceived) to outsource significant aspects of production. Handmaking processes have long imposed natural limits upon entrepreneurial growth for craftspeople, as evident in the legendary artistic and cultural—but limited financial—success, for example, of the British Arts and Crafts Movement or German Bauhaus. Designers however are not bound by such limitations of scale, with their practice based on outsourcing production once they feel they have resolved prototypes ready for marketable replication. Hence the emergence of the figure of the designer maker in the contemporary 'handmade' marketplace as a mode of operation that does, potentially, enable scalable growth. But both because there is anxiety around the question: 'when does something cease to be 'handmade'?', as well as ongoing concerns around whose hands make things (do they need to be the person's behind the brand?; were they paid well?; are their working conditions fair and safe?), while some people are happily outsourcing designs and reaping the financial rewards of growth, more makers than we expected remained either ethically or aesthetically opposed to scalable growth. Significantly, others simply did not wish to grow; for them the challenge was actually *not* getting (too) big, flying in the face of the neoliberal entrepreneurial agendas:

Q. Is employing other people something you are thinking about? Or outsourcing?

A: It was not previously, I have trouble of letting go of the reigns" (Male, Emerging Maker, Furniture Design)

“..... mass produced stuff I’ve seen enough of that in shops that I’ve worked in and I think it’s soulless; it doesn’t have that something that somebody’s two hands put this together. Or if you can see those marks and it was imported from overseas, what were those poor people paid? I mean that might be a suicidal business decision if you wanted to be a hardnose business person, but I really like to relate to the people that buy my stuff and go: “Oh, so you made this?” And I’m like “Yeah.” (Female, Established Maker, Jewellery)

“I wouldn’t be happy to outsource the final finishing process. I think one of the things is if people buy something off you they and you’re spouting yourself as design and maker you actually have to physically get involved with the making, and I think quality control goes down pretty quickly if you’re outsourcing everything and you’re just putting it in a box I couldn’t imagine getting to the stage where I was just doing a design and sending the files everywhere and never seeing them again, but never say never, but yeah I don’t ever plan on being that sort of a designer.” (Male, Emerging Maker, Furniture Design)

“What, I’ve always been really clear with this business, that it only makes sense as long as I enjoy doing it. And you know it’s, I think it’s a very slippery slope in Australia, as soon as you’re paying wages and you need a bigger workshop, you just end up offshore ...” (Male, Established Maker, Shoemaker)

A: “I won’t outsource anything.

Q: No?

A: Because it’s not, I don’t want to, I just don’t – first of all I don’t want that responsibility of being responsible for someone else’s income in a way, so and plus I’m a bit of a control freak; I used to be a project manager and you know I don’t want any impacts on my business. I want to manage my whole business, and a lot of the courses that I’ve talked about are maybe you could outsource if my business needs to be outsourced I’ve gotten too big and I’ll scale it back. So I feel like at the moment I am as big as what I can be, I’m as busy as what I can be, I don’t want to get any busier; it means too many compromises. (Female, Established Maker, Flameworking/Glass Beads)

Q: “I was going to say you’ve lived the highs and lows of a large business and you want to keep this to the joys still?

A: The joys of it, and I want to come to work every day and be in control and love what I do, and not be consumed by something that has turned into a business that is starting to manage itself, and it’s very easy for that to happen.” (Female, Established Maker, Fashion Accessories)

Resonating through these quotes is the idea of ‘craft’ as an adjective; a marker of quality, provenance, artistry. In short, of a particular relation to art and making. What persists here, despite repeated attempts over centuries to contain the autonomy of the craft worker including most recently the individualising governmentality implicit in neoliberal creative industries policy and

discourse, is a resistance to control and containment within capitalist 'business as usual' (Banks 2006). A further implicit part of this challenge if not overt resistance to hegemonic understanding of entrepreneurial success, one that cannot be separated from both the artistic and crafts guild legacies of the practices as well as the prominence of women within the sector, is the presence of mutual support and not just competition between designer makers and craftspeople. As also noted by other researchers of cultural entrepreneurialism (Naudin 2018), whether it be through collectively organising studio space, sharing business information or practice-based skills, or more general moral support, a notable feature of the Australian design craft landscape is a sense of solidarity that is a far cry from the combative competition that is such a feature of business enterprise television shows such as *The Apprentice*.

III. Later stage of life-related reasons for starting a creative business: 'downshifting' not 'starting up'

The desire to limit business growth also lay in the catalysts among our participants for starting their creative business. In her work on the UK's mumpreneurs, Ekinsmyth's research reveals that for many of her respondents the choice to identify as a 'mumpreneur' rather than 'entrepreneur' is a very deliberate one chosen for a number of reasons including the networking possibilities this identification opens up; the desire to make a clear statement about the need for motherhood and successful economic participation to be reconcilable in the contemporary economy; and, to make a statement about 'the way' that they conduct their business (Ekinsmyth 2011, p. 109). Notably, this includes for many the decision to not get too big, to not grow beyond a desired level of work-life manageability (Ekinsmyth 2011). As we have seen, this is certainly also reflected in our study, including in the reasons given by many of the mothers we spoke to hoping to balance income-generating work and motherhood.

This is something we have written about at some length already (Luckman 2015; Luckman and Andrew 2018 & 2019), but it is worth repeating here that with many parents, and women in particular, seeking out home-based self-employment as an imperfect solution to family-unfriendly workplaces, it is inevitable that large sections of the design craft economy have natural barriers to growth at the level of the individual. In this way, I would argue that the growth of this sector as a whole is in many ways less a function of successful government creative or cultural policy, as much as a perfect storm of digital technology enabling a face and soul-saving retreat to the home for professional women in the face of the failure of affordable childcare and family friendly workplace agendas, coupled with the growth of discourses of intensive mothering. By face-saving, I refer to the workforce identity running a business—no matter how small the turnover—affords women both to themselves and in response to the inevitable social question: "what do you do?" For these are generally tertiary educated accustomed to having a paid work identity. Despite the rise of intensive mothering discourses, for many of these women in shades of Friedan's 'problem that has no name' (Friedan 1963), there is a very specific driver behind their business start-up motivations:

"So [when both my children grew a little older] I had time during the day where they were both sleeping during the day and I started getting immensely bored, I'm not an awesome born to be mother anyway. So it's not like that fulfils me completely, but I

started getting really bored and really quite miserable about that. creatively I was lacking immensely and it was affecting my wellbeing. So I decided I had to start, had doing creative stuff again. (Female, Established Maker, Resin Jewellery)

“So, and I was like, oh, gosh, I’ll go mad if I just sit at home, and so, I started doing a class at Fremantle Art Centre, and I just basically never stopped.” (Female, Established Maker, Ceramics)

Here, the ‘choice’ to be working from home sounds less freely chosen, but for many of our participants – women, men and couples – their creative micro-enterprise was part of a planned and desired commitment to achieving greater balance and happiness in their life. Of realising dreams of ‘downshifting’ (often to rural or peri-urban locations, with all the lifestyle and self-sufficiency affordances they offer), not scaling up:

“I’m not looking to have enough money to buy a house for myself, I don’t mind if I rent for the rest of my life. I’ve never been in a good financial situation because of the struggle with health. I just want to keep going through life and enjoying life as I go, rather than killing myself to have some end goal and then realising I should have enjoyed it while it while I was young.” (Male, Established Maker, Recycled Bike Part Accessories)

“It’s very opportune that you sort of gave us a call now because I’ve being in the web development world for a couple of decades or more, I’ve had enough and I’m actually in the process of selling my share in the business and actually going out and doing more of this [creative making] work. (Male, Established Maker, Bespoke Dog Collars)

IV. Quality handmaking as an environmentally-sympathetic response to a world of ‘too much stuff’ and climate crisis

As already inferred in some of the quotes above, a concern for the environmental impacts of their practice was a further key driver limiting the maker’s desire for entrepreneurial growth. This was manifest across the production process, for example in concern for everything from the sourcing of materials; electricity generation and use; the making practices and techniques themselves; and ultimately thoughtfulness around how much, and what, stuff they were willing to produce. This was often conducted with an attention to the traditional crafts ethos of building quality and ‘to last’, and with the potential to repair rather than replace:

“No I wouldn’t outsource it [production]. it’s not important enough for me to see it grow and, because I have a hard time with more and more stuff being in the world.” (Female, Emerging Maker, Glass)

“Q: in the future would you be looking potentially to employ other people, or would it be more about outsourcing production?”

A: Outsourcing production, but still keeping the bits that I like to do so the hand knitting – there would always be a component of a handmade something even if it meant my website was five jumpers that are machine made and then a one off handmade piece. the idea of it growing so big that I would have to go offshore scares me frankly.

Q: Unethical labour sounds like it is a concern of yours?

A: It definitely is and I don't actually want to make that much stuff. Like we have got so much stuff..... I don't want to make heaps of stuff." (Female, Emerging Maker, Textile Designer)

"So at the moment I'm collecting things from op shops, and just ferreting them away and I've got a box and because ultimately I'd like to make all my work from recycled materials that's where I'm heading." (Female, Established Maker, Jewellery)

".... this type of furniture that we're making, they're pretty bulletproof. There's not much that you can do that can't be repaired. And we say that. They might change and grow out of how – I mean obviously if you buy a table that's a 16-seater, at some point in your life you might downsize and move to a smaller house but the table doesn't get thrown out, it gets handed on. And you might come to us as a young couple that's living in a share accommodation or in rental accommodation and you might have something really small and at some point you get to a bigger house and you need something bigger. But that table still gets repurposed as a desk in an office space or something. So the pieces have – and we say to them we can always help if they do need a hand moving it or if it needs to be refinished or what have you, all that sort of stuff. That's part of when you make a connection with a local maker you can actually do that. It's an ongoing relationship." (Female, Established Maker, Furniture Maker)

"Certainly, the way I print reduces waste, because people are always asking me for scraps. Well, I don't have any, because I make all these fridge magnets. so any bit on a piece of fabric that's too small to fit a sunglasses case or something, I fill it up with those. So, out of a metre I only have these little tiny scraps." (Female, Established Maker, Textiles)

As production and materials specialists, many craftspeople and designer makers are drawn to working creatively to develop more sustainable modes of making. Again the issue of scale is key here. Many makers seek to be part of challenging the 'growth' narrative, and clearly most are very much aware of their environmental impacts. A post-growth opportunity to be mobilised here lies in the skillsets, implicit knowledges and deep understandings of materials and processes craftspeople can bring to the how we make in a post-growth, climate crisis age. This includes the capacity to tinker, to play, to repair, to re-use for 'waste' is always on the move, always becoming, and potentially being un-made, re-used.

V. *Still artists at heart: doing 'what you love' (which isn't running a business).*

The overall picture that emerges from many of the interviews is that despite all the creative industries incentives and language around 'entrepreneurship', creative business development, and self-promotion, many designer makers and craftspeople still fundamentally wish to, and do, see themselves more as artists than entrepreneurs or even business people, let alone employers or managers:

"That's right; I want to do the creative stuff. I don't want to be stuck in being a manager. I'm not an entrepreneur. It's not what I am." (Female, Established Maker, Textiles)

"And I wanted to make. I think I've always said to myself, if you can make enough money from your art to live I'll be content. That's just my benchmark. I don't need to be world famous or anything, I just need to make a living doing the things that I love doing." (Female, Established Maker, Jewellery)

"For me it's not about the money which I know sounds ridiculous because I am trying to run a business, but business is the word that I can that's the only word I can give it because that's all that's been afforded to [us]. But to me it's an experience, it's a relationship, and I know that's what business is as well but it has to have depth to it. I want it to become more community focussed in the sense that I would like to be able to become more philanthropic in what I do, and have that as a side to my business so that whatever I earn, a certain amount of that can then go towards other things that I feel passionately about. (Female, Emerging Maker, Metal Design)

One way in which the desire to maintain a focus on the artistic, creative and/or making side of their business is practically enabled is not through the outsourcing and thus scaling up of production, but rather of the other tasks required of the self-employed. Notably, the less desirable managing a business type tasks. Increasingly, with the normalisation of online including social media promotion, this also includes the once considered more creative or recreational activity of online promotion and networking. In this way, outsourcing tasks associated with the online performativity that is a new normal of contemporary creative economies is a contemporary marker of middle class privilege, and alongside more traditional business support services (such as accountancy, business planning, photography, website development), into the future is potentially a more likely area for expansion in the economy than making itself:

"Ideally it would be great to hire someone to do the admin or the networking side of things or whatever, but that's not realistic at the moment." (Female, Emerging Maker, Glass)

A: "No, I wouldn't outsource the making of the resin, I would outsource the accounting side of things and the more

Q: Other services, complimentary services to your business?

A: Yeah, exactly." (Female, Established Maker, Resin Jewellery and Tableware)

“I would happily outsource social media if it got to a point where that was worthwhile, I would definitely outsource my accounting because that is totally not my niche at all, and it just is hard work.” (Female, Established Maker, Resin Jewellery)

“..... we don't have other people working with us at the moment and if I did, it might be in production but it would probably more likely be in an area like marketing or PR.” (Female, Emerging Maker, Woodworker)

Conclusion

Clearly “the resources to become an entrepreneurial subject [even a reluctant one] are unevenly distributed” (Scharff 2016, p. 109). But the dream of ‘being one’s own boss’ and ‘doing what you love’ are compelling and persistent ones, with anticipation of sustainable self-employment continuing today to drive the ‘hope labour’ (Kuehn and Corrigan, 2013) of artists, craftspeople and other creative practitioners. But while “being the captain of your own ship” [may be] a cultural ideal more glamorous in fantasy than in reality” (Dudley 2014, p. 3), self-employment and risk-taking still emerge in the minds of those who pursue it as less complicity in neoliberal capitalism, and rather as a trade-off worth making in a world of economic, political and social precarity. The prevalence in this sector of a desire to chart an alternative entrepreneurial course is notable for the way it crosses across stage of career and areas of practice. In so doing, ‘entrepreneurship’ is re-imagined, albeit generally not rejected, for the enculturation into neoliberal ideals experienced by middle class communities across the industrialised world means that much resistance or fighting back against the entrepreneurial imperative remains variously compromised, as well as often driven by (enlightened) self-interest. This gives rise to important, and age-old, questions around the complicity of the liberal middle class in the status quo; should not their energy go into more active and clear resistance?

But perhaps what is more valuable to identify here as the basis for wider solidarity and mobilisation for change is the clear resistance to the inevitability of business and production growth as an unquestioned good in the face of climate change and world filled with too much ‘stuff’. While many of the makers we have spoken to want to ‘make a good living’ from their practice; importantly ‘good’ here refers to a not only financial reward but also operating a business in keeping with their value systems. As repeatedly stated, it is impossible to ignore the reality that to be able to do so is an act of relative privilege. But it also is an example of the progressive potential of micro-economic activity within an “intentional economy” which seek to use its business practices to address social and environmental problems (Gibson-Graham 2006). In advocating for the creative economy to be subject to the limits of a post-growth world, many of these otherwise idealised neoliberal subjects do actively challenge conventional capitalist ideas of what ‘success’ looks like. This has important policy implications for the kinds of start-up incentives, business support and reward structures available to the creatively self-employed given many of the existing mechanisms tend to assume a normatively masculine and hyper-capitalist vision of success and motivation. Models for reimagining capitalism in an age of climate crisis exist; the challenge now is their accessible mainstreaming into the broader social and economic landscape.

Acknowledgements

This research was supported under the Australian Research Council's Discovery Project funding scheme (project number DP150100485 'Promoting the Making Self in the Creative Micro-Economy'). I thank Belinda Powles her invaluable input and assistance with the research project and, as always, the makers who have generously shared their stories with us. Thank-you also to the three anonymous reviews for their feedback and suggestions for improvements. I would also like to acknowledge the valuable support provided by the University of Leeds via the Cheney Fellowship that helped bring this paper into being.

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